

BANK LOAN OFFICERS' PERCEPTIONS OF CORPORATE FINANCIAL DISCLOSURE IN THE BANKING SECTOR OF BANGLADESH: AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

Dr. Madan Mohan Dey Alim Al Ayub Ahmed***

Abstract

All financial disclosure i. e., mandatory disclosure and voluntary disclosure are both included in an effective information disclosure system. Mandatory disclosure is the basic demand of the market, and voluntary disclosure is the extended demand of the market, because of its informative complement to the timing, content and depth of disclosure. Some specific disclosure includes the laws governing the formations of banks; the by-laws established by the bank itself, and the structure of the bank. The issue of the corporate financial disclosure is receiving greater attention both the developed and developing countries in the corporate sectors particularly. Nevertheless, this issue still remains largely unfamiliar in the corporate arena of the banking sector of Bangladesh. This study focuses on the practices of some selected disclosure practicing through annual reports by banks operating in Bangladesh. For this paper, an empirical study as well as a questionnaire survey has been conducted. The principal findings include, firstly, most of the banks discloses the name of default directors with amount due, the name of borrower directors, prepares aging schedule, fixes the rate of provisions for bad debts, do not take qualified opinion or disclaimer, creates secret reserves in the balance-sheet and uses cost principle in valuing assets and secondly the respondents are in favor of such disclosures. As it is requirement, the current disclosures are not ample in evaluating the goals of corporate financial disclosure in the banking sector.

** Professor, Department of Accounting and Information Systems, Rajshahi University

* Lecturer in Accounting, School of Business, Asian University of Bangladesh

Keywords

Financial Disclosure, Bank Loan Officer (BLO), Bangladesh

1. Introduction

The aim of the present research is to enhance our understanding of the corporate financial reporting disclosure environment in Bangladesh by seeking the opinions of the Bank Loan Officers that are expected to be affected by such an environment. Our objective therefore is to discover the major corporate information sources to the major interested parties in the banking sector in Bangladesh. Such a study will also shed light on how corporate financial disclosure prepares and regulators can improve the current corporate reporting practices as well as provide rich description of some aspects of financial accounting and its environment in Bangladesh. Although the subject of the present research is not a new one, it is, however, handled more thoroughly and has a broader scope than previous research attempts. There is a paucity of research regarding users' information needs in developing countries. There are studies of Wallace (1988a; 1988b) in Nigeria and Nicholls and Ahmed (1995) in Bangladesh, which measured the quality of disclosure taking into consideration the perception of users in a developing country perspective. This chapter analyzes the results of the questionnaire survey among a sample of bank loan officers. The main trust of this paper is to focus the perception of the users (BLO) about their perceived importance for various sources of information in making their decisions, reasons for using financial information, and their opinions regarding the adequacy and reliability of information of annual reports. Different users groups have different objectives in using financial reports and it has been pointed out that they may have diverse informational needs (Benjamin and Stanga, 1977; p.187).

2. Objectives of the Study

The destination of this study is to focus the perception of the BLO as users about their perceived importance for various sources of information in making their decisions, and their opinions regarding the adequacy and reliability of information of annual reports. This study attempts to focus on the present scenario of corporate financial disclosure by the banks of Bangladesh in their annual reports. Objectives of this study cover the followings:

- a) To have an idea about the perception of BLOs regarding the importance of various items of disclosure in decision-making.
- b) To examine the opinion of BLOs regarding adequacy and reliability of corporate annual reports.
- e) To suggests some measures to take a sound corporate financial report by the banking companies.

3. Methodology

The article is based on empirical study as well as questionnaire survey i. e. primary information. For the purpose of the study, the questionnaires were sent to 20 bank loan officers (BLO) of different banks.

3.1. Method of Data Collection

This part of the paper considers the research methodology of the present study. The aim of this phase is to set up the foundation of the statistical analysis. The researchers have used direct interview method to collect response for the respondents at Rajshahi. In this context, we have prepared a questionnaire to collect the necessary data. We shall use this method to avoid non-response bias by the respondents. In case of some respondents from Dhaka and Bogra the questionnaire were sent through mail.

3.2. Preparation of Questionnaire

We have prepared a questionnaire to collect opinion of the respondents about the voluntary disclosure which judges the quality of information disclosed in financial statements. The questionnaire used was divided into two parts, PART-1 and PART-2. The PART-1 included questions representing the name, occupation, age, educational and professional qualifications, accountancy training of the respondent. The number of questions included in PART-2 asked to bankers, which dealt with their perception of disclosed items in the financial statements. The total number of questions included in PART-1 was 9 and PART-2, 10 to 21.

3.3. Number of Respondents

Our survey will cover a sample of 20 bank loan officers. Among the total of 20 questionnaire issued, 17 respondents gave valuable feedback regarding the questionnaire while others were reluctant to give any information regarding this. This chapter represents the sources of data that were collected for this study. The questionnaire surveys from BLO play a very important role in the study. To conduct a questionnaire survey is a difficult task on the part of any researcher. In any questionnaire survey the response rate may be very low if the questionnaire is mailed to the respondents.

3.4. Questions solicited

The questionnaire for the current study was pre-tested with personnel of accounting department, prominent academicians, and researchers. The respondents were again supplied with the questionnaire two weeks after they had filled up first questionnaire. The final questionnaire for the

study contained a covering letter and a brief background of the study. In the covering letter, it was mentioned that the researcher was conducting the study as part of PhD thesis, so that the respondents would understand that the study is sponsored which might increase changes of better responses. Identifying the perceptions of various bank loan officers about the disclosure of the selected items of voluntary information in the banks annual reports through a questionnaire survey constitutes the main part of the study. The first part of the final version of questionnaire included questions representing the name, occupation, age, accounting training, educational qualifications of the respondents and the second part contained voluntary disclosure information of the banks stated earlier. The questionnaire used in the survey is presented in Appendix. To make this paper more informative different published textbooks, related journals, reports, seminar papers and research works have been analyzed. The questionnaire survey method, regardless of its inherent drawbacks seemed appropriate for this type of study. Survey method is most appropriate and effective for drawing conclusion regarding peoples' inference and attitudes (Carmichale and Swieringa, 1968). The response rate of the survey among the respondents is discussed in the empirical part of the paper.

4. Response rate

The questionnaire survey consists of a sample of 20 bank loan officers as indicated in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1: *Response Rate of the Questionnaire Survey*

User Group	Sam ple Size	No. of Responses	Rate of Response (%)
Bank Loan Officers	20	17	85

Table 4.1 showed the specified user group of the respondents and the size of the sample of the respondents. It also describes the response rate of the questionnaire survey from bank loan officer. Questionnaires were sent to 20 BLOs of the scheduled banks of Bangladesh. The respondents were requested to reply as early as possible for a significant involvement in the study. All the respondents were sent reminders through mobile about 10 days after the questionnaire were sent. Within two weeks of sending, 17 responses were received. The 17 usable responses constituted a response rate of 85 percent, which is acceptable. The response rate is above the rate mentioned by Moser and Kalton (1971) and Ali, Khan Fatima and Masud (2008) as being sufficient for a study leading to policymaking.

5. Review of the related literature

It is widely accepted that corporate annual reports are prepared primarily for external users. Therefore, such reports should be designed, in form and content, according to the needs of the external users (Radebough, and Gray, 1993). These users should be contacted frequently to assess their perceptions about various aspects of the reporting practices of public companies since their views will provide the main feedback to improve the communication function of corporate reports (Epstein, 1993).

One of the pioneering studies to have attempted to discover the information needs and sources of such information was undertaken in the United States by Baker and Haslem in 1973. The authors found that the majority of the individual investors rely heavily on stockbroker's advice as their main source of information about companies. Financial statements, however, were found to be a source of information by only a minority (i.e., 8 per cent) of individual investors. Regarding other information items that are expected to be disclosed by companies, Baker and Haslem (1973) highlight that individual investors attach a great deal of importance to the information about the future expectations of the company. At the same time, individual investors attached a much lower degree of importance to information regarding dividends.

Anderson (1981) also recognized the need for research in this area and focused on institutional investors in Australia. He sought, primarily, to discover their perceptions about the importance of annual corporate reports to their decision making process by analyzing the responses of 188 institutional investors. Anderson (1981) found that Australian investors relied mostly on the annual report when making their investment decisions followed by visits to the companies. Regarding the annual corporate report itself, the most readable sections of the annual report were the balance sheet, profit and loss account, notes to the accounts, and the chairman's statement respectively, The profit and loss account, however, was perceived to be more important than the balance sheet. However, the author failed to perform any statistical test to determine whether there is a significant difference between the users' usage of the annual report sections on the one hand and the perceived importance of such sections on the other hand. Anderson (1981) also documents the external users' desire (i.e., 72 per cent) for additional information to be provided in the annual corporate report such as information about the company's product, current value of long-term assets, and remuneration of directors.

Anderson and Epstein (1995) further extended their research by providing a useful investigation on Australia. Unlike the Anderson (1981) study, which specifically focused on Australian institutional investors, the Anderson and Epstein (1995) study was more concerned

with individual investors' usage of annual corporate reports. Their findings revealed that the annual corporate reports came third, after stockbrokers' advice and financial newspapers and magazines, as a basis for investment decision of Australian individual investors. Nevertheless, the vast majority of their respondents (i.e., 72 per cent) perceived annual corporate reports to be of only moderate use. Regarding the use of the annual report, the authors highlight the directors' report to be the most thoroughly read followed by the income statement. Nevertheless, their respondents did perceive the income statement to be more useful than the directors' report in making an investment decision. Arguably, Anderson and Epstein (1995) did not statistically determine whether the difference between the pattern of readership of the annual reports' sections and the perceived usefulness of such sections is of any significance in the Australian environment. Respondents had also expressed a desire for the simplification and more explanation of the balance sheet, statement of cash flow, and the income statement. Finally, the authors highlight the Australian investors' demand for additional disclosure in the annual reports; such as pending litigation, unasserted claims, management audit, and information on change of auditor.

In another Middle Eastern environment, Jordan, Abu-Nassar and Rutherford (1996) undertook a study to discover the view of external users of annual corporate reports. The authors targeted different groups of external users, namely individual shareholders, institutional shareholders, bank loan officers, stockbrokers, and academics. Their sample comprised of 224 respondents and all of their analyses are of a unvaried type. In terms of the usage of the annual report, Abu-Nassar and Rutherford (1996) found bank loan officers to be the heaviest users of the annual reports in Jordan while individual shareholders and academics were found to be the least. They also found the income statement and balance sheet to be the most widely read parts of the annual corporate report by all the users. The authors documented the low degree of users' satisfaction about many qualitative characteristics of corporate reports in Jordan. In terms of the importance of the various sources of corporate information, Abu-Nassar and Rutherford (1996) argue the annual corporate report to be the most important source of information for all user groups. The only exception being the bank loan officers who indicated that the most important source of information to them was to personally visit companies followed by an independent examination of the annual report itself.

Ali, Khan, Fatima and Masud (2008) provide a useful survey of the attitudes of individual respondents on the various aspects of Bangladeshi annual corporate reports. They analyzed the responses of 25 individual

investors and found firstly, British American Tobacco (BAT) Bangladesh Co. Ltd makes very few disclosures on corporate governance on a voluntary basis and secondly, the user groups of the annual reports are in favor of such disclosure. The researchers further found that the current disclosures are not ample in evaluating the goal of corporate governance.

6. Data analysis

6.1 Academic achievement of respondents

Table 6.1 shows the overall respondent’ academic achievements. Table 6.1 shows that 17.6% of the respondents have graduate education and 82.4% of the respondents have a Masters.

Table 6.1: *Academic achievement of respondents*

Educational Qualification		Total
		B.L.O.
Bachelor	Count % within res.gr.	3 17.6%
Masters	Count % within res.gr.	14 82.4%
Ph.D.	Count % within res.gr.	0 0.00%
Total	Count % within res.gr.	17 100.0%

Table 6.4: *Accounting Qualification of the Respondents*

Accounting Qualifications		Total
		B.L.O.
None	Count % within res.gr.	11 64.7%
Worked/working as a bookkeeper	Count % within res.gr.	1 5.9%
Attended appropriate course(s) in accounting	Count % within res.gr.	0 0.0%
Hold accounting qualifications	Count % within res.gr.	2 11.8%
Served/serving as an accountant executive	Count % within res.gr.	2 11.8%

Served as accounting teaching profession	Count % within res.gr.	1 5.9%
Total	Count % within res.gr.	17 100.0%

6.5 Opinion of the respondents regarding preparation of Aging Schedule

The bank loan officers were asked to respond regarding the preparation of aging schedule. The responses are summarized in Table 6.5.

Table 6.5

		B L O
No	Count % within	4 23.53%
Yes	Count % within	13 76.47%
Total	Count % within	17 100.0%

Table 6.5 shows that 76.47% of the bankers responded positively and 23.53% of the banker don’t prepare aging schedule of loans and advances.

6.6 Opinion of the respondents regarding fixation of rate of provisions for bad debts

The bank loan officers were asked to respond regarding fixation of the rate of provisions for bad debts. The responses are summarized in Table 6.6.

Table 6.6

		B L O
No	Count % within	1 5.88%
Yes	Count % within	16 94.12%
Total	Count % within	17 100.0%

Table 6.6 shows that 94.12% of the banker opined that they fix the rate of provisions for bad debts.

6.7 Opinion of the respondents regarding receiving qualified opinion

The bank loan officers were asked to respond regarding receiving qualified opinion or disclaimer. The responses are summarized in Table 6.7.

Table 6.7

		B L O
No	Count % within	14 82.35%
Yes	Count % within	3 17.65%
Total	Count % within	17 100.0%

Table 6.7 shows that 82.35% of the banker responded that they have not received qualified opinion.

6.8 Opinion of the respondents regarding creating secret reserves in balance-sheet

The bank loan officers were asked to respond regarding creating secret reserves in balance sheet. The responses are summarized in Table 6.8.

Table 6.8

		B L O
No	Count % within	3 17.65%
Yes	Count % within	14 82.35%
Total	Count % within	17 100.0%

Table 6.8 shows that 82.35% of the banker responded that they create secret reserves in their balance sheet.

6.9 Opinion of the respondents regarding use of cost principle in valuing their assets

The bank loan officers were asked to respond regarding the use of cost principle in valuing their assets. The responses are summarized in Table 6.9.

Table 6.9

		B L O
No	Count % within	2 13.3%
Yes	Count % within	15 88.24%
Total	Count % within	17 100.0%

Table 6.9 shows that 88.24% of the banker opined that they use cost principle in valuing their assets.

6.10 Opinion of the respondents regarding disclosure of information in annual reports if cost principle is not followed

The bank loan officers were asked to respond whether disclosure is made in corporate annual reports if the bank did not follow cost principle. The responses are summarized in Table 6.10.

Table 6.10

		B L O
No	Count % within	2 13.3%
Yes	Count % within	15 88.24%
Total	Count % within	17 100.0%

Table 6.10 shows that 88.24% of the banker responded that if cost principle is not followed, they disclose that information in the annual reports.

6.11 Opinion of the respondents regarding adequacy of disclosure in annual reports

The information disclosed by companies in their annual reports should be adequate for the economic decision-making. Without adequate

information the present and prospective shareholders or investors must find it difficult to make their investment decisions. Keeping this point in mind, in the questionnaire, the respondents were asked if they thought that annual reports contain adequate information necessary to serve their purposes in using them. The responses are summarized in Table 6.11.

Table 6.11: *Opinion of the respondents regarding adequacy of disclosure in annual reports*

		B.L.O.
Fully adequate	Count % within	7 41.2%
Partially adequate	Count % within	9 52.9%
Not adequate	Count % within	1 5.9%
Total	Count % within	17 100.0%

Table 6.11 shows that 5.9% of the respondents thought that the annual reports were ‘not adequate’; while majority of them thought that they were either partially adequate (52.9%) or fully adequate (41.2%).

6.12 Opinion of the respondents regarding reliability of information in annual reports

Adequacy and reliability are two important qualitative characteristics that should be followed by the banks in their corporate annual reports. The information disclosed by banks in their annual reports should be reliable for the economic decision-making. Without the reliability of information the present and prospective shareholders or investors must find it difficult to make their investment decisions. Keeping this point in mind, in the questionnaire, the respondents were asked if they thought that annual reports contain reliability of information necessary to serve their purposes in using them. The responses are summarized in Table 6.12.

Table 6.12: *Opinion of the respondents regarding reliability of information in annual reports*

		B.L.O.
Fully reliable	Count % within	5 29.4%
Partially reliable	Count % within	8 47.1%

Not reliable	Count % within	4 23.5%
Total	Count % within	17 100.0%

Table 6.12 shows that 23.5% of the respondents thought that the annual reports were ‘not reliable’; while majority of them thought that they were either partially reliable (47.1%) or fully reliable (29.4%).

6.13 Opinion of the respondents regarding the satisfaction of reporting requirements

The bank loan officers were asked to respond regarding their satisfaction with the present reporting requirements and present reporting practices. The responses are summarized in Table 6.13.

Table 6.13

Are you happy with the present-		reporting requirements	reporting practices
No	Count % within	3 17.65%	4 23.53%
Yes	Count % within	14 82.35%	13 76.47%
Total	Count % within	17 100.0%	17 100.0%

Table 6.13 shows that 82.35% and 76.47% of the respondents express their satisfaction on present reporting requirements and present reporting practices respectively.

6.14 Opinion of the respondents regarding disclosure of the name of default directors with amount due in notes to financial statements

Table 6.14

		BLO
No	Count % within	15 88.24%
Yes	Count % within	2 11.76%
Total	Count % within	17 100.0%

Table 6.14 shows that only 11.76% of the respondents disclose the name of default directors with amount due in notes to financial statements.

Most of the respondents (88.24%) don't disclose the name of default directors.

6.15 Opinion of the respondents regarding disclosure of the name of borrower directors in notes to financial statements

Table 6.15

		BLO
No	Count	16
	% within	94.12%
Yes	Count	1
	% within	5.88%
Total	Count	17
	% within	100.0%

Table 6.15 shows that only 5.88% of the respondents disclose the name of borrower directors in notes to financial statements. Most of the respondents (94.12%) don't disclose the name of borrower directors.

6.16 Opinion of the respondents regarding disclosure of the name of Business enterprises of the borrower directors

Table 6.16

		BLO
No	Count	17
	% within BLO	100.0%
Yes	Count	0
	% within BLO	0.0%
Total	Count	17
	% within BLO	100.0%

Table 6.16 shows that no respondents disclose the name of business enterprises of the borrower directors. 100.0% respondents don't disclose the name of business enterprises of borrower directors.

7. Major findings

Though corporate financial disclosure is an on-going concept in the banking sector, some weaknesses of the reports may be identified. The paper revealed the following key findings:

- ❑ No respondents disclose the name of business enterprises of borrower directors.
- ❑ With regard to disclosing the name of borrower directors in notes to financial statements a significant number of respondents held the opinion that they don't disclose the name of borrower directors.

- ❑ Again most of the BLO take the view that they don't disclose the name of default directors.
- ❑ The BLOs were asked to respond regarding their satisfaction with the present reporting requirements and present reporting practices. A majority of the BLO expressed their satisfaction on present reporting requirements and present reporting practices.
- ❑ The findings also reported that most of the bankers use cost principle in valuing their assets. Further they reported that if cost principle is not followed, they disclose that information in the annual reports.
- ❑ Majority of respondent thought that annual reports were either partially reliable (47.1%) or fully reliable (29.4%).
- ❑ Majority of respondent thought that annual reports were either partially adequate (52.9%) or fully adequate (41.2%).
- ❑ As the whistleblower most of the respondents state that they create secret reserves in their balance sheet.
- ❑ The findings cover also the soundness of the corporate financial disclosure of the banks that greater portion of the banker prepare aging schedule of loans and advances, they fix the rate of provisions for bad debts and they have not received qualified opinion or disclaimer.
- ❑ It is important to note that percentages for yes/no answer calculated from the total number who answered the questions as opposed to the total number of surveys distributed, this was done to prevent any distortion in the survey findings.

8. Limitations of the Study

- ❑ The study is based on empirical evidences and several areas of asymmetry have been illuminated.
- ❑ The authors have done the analysis on the basis of semi-structured primary data and some secondary data.
- ❑ For preparing the paper the authors only consider BLO as respondents and several respondent groups like Professional Accountants, Stock Brokers, Financial Analysts, and Accounting Professors have been avoided.

9. Conclusion and recommendations

Annual reports, to a large extent, form the basis for action by investors, creditors and potential creditors of the banks. Because of this, shareholders, in particular, must understand in general way the contents of annual report. This study examines the perceptions of major user group, namely bank loan officer. The study reveals that the corporate

annual report of banking company was the most important source of corporate information to the entire participating user group. This report provides an overview of the results pertinent to the questionnaire survey regarding disclosure policy of the commercial banks. The report offers a summary of the perception of key senior experts of BLO, pertaining to the disclosure policy of banks' level of compliance with best practice in corporate governance. This report provides an overview of the results pertinent to the Corporate Governance Survey of the Bangladeshi Banking Sector. Among the majority of respondents, the questionnaires were completed by representatives of the banks' top management, (e.g. Assistant General Managers) as well as heads of business divisions (e.g. Head of Compliance, Chief of Internal Audit). Respondents have in place a good general framework for corporate governance more emphasis is needed in the area of conducting structured reporting on compliance with good disclosure practices. More policies are needed to address minority rights and more efforts need to be geared toward designing and implementing special training programs on corporate governance and internal control practices for employees. Independent directors do not have a majority presence in the boardroom Banks, in general, do not take into consideration the evaluation of client's financial reporting practices in their credit risk assessment. Banks should have special committees for supervising and monitoring major business functions. Banks have already given much effort in the field of corporate financial disclosure in their annual reports. But still now some voluntary essential requirement exists; the current accounting system should make it mandatory for the stakeholders of banks. Corporate financial disclosure should be presented in classified form such as name of default directors with amount due, the name of borrower directors, Aging Schedule, fixing the rate of provisions for bad debts, qualified opinion or disclaimer, creating secret reserves in the balance-sheet, using cost principle in valuing assets, labor management relationship, environmental contribution in separate headings. As it is voluntary requirement, all banks do not disclose corporate social responsibility in monetary terms. So the transparency of the corporate social responsibility report sometimes makes question mark to the user groups. To resolve this problem the Government of Bangladesh should make it mandatory to disclose the corporate social responsibility information with financial data. Accounting should develop a standard to guide the practice of corporate financial disclosure and reporting with which the company can make a compliance report the corporate governance disclosure.

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